

VALENTINA AKIMENKO. FEATURES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF DISTANCE LEARNING FOR SPEECH THERAPIST STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES (pp. 33-41)

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

FEATURES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF DISTANCE LEARNING FOR SPEECH THERAPIST STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES

Akimenko Valentina Mikhailovna
Associate Professor of the Department
of Defectology and Inclusive Education,
Ph.D., Associate Professor,
Stavropol State Pedagogical Institute
Stavropol, Russia
ORCID: 0000-0001-8589-1452

Keywords: virtual laboratories, speech therapy platform, speech therapist students, examination, modeling of work situations, correctional work, practical classes

Abstract. The article provides an analysis of the main trends in modern education, characterized by the introduction of distance learning, variability in the choice of courses and pace of learning, the prevalence of individual curricula, the use of artificial intelligence, etc. The experience of using special services that allow speech therapists to master many types of remedial work provided for in the plan of practical classes in the mode of modeling work situations is presented. The experience of compiling material for virtual distance practical classes, which is organized in such a way as to create the basis for students' own reasoning, the formation of professional skills, is described. their search for additional facts, their analysis and generalization.

Introduction

Trends in modern learning are constantly changing and evolving as education adapts to new technologies and social changes. Today, distance learning is quite firmly entering the process of teaching schoolchildren and students.

Distance learning is a form of learning in which students gain knowledge and skills remotely without visiting physical educational institutions. Distance learning is conducted online using various technologies such as video conferences, webinars, e-textbooks, tests, etc. [4].

One of the key factors in the success of distance learning is the quality of teaching materials and methods. Distance learning provides an opportunity to use modern technologies and tools that allow students to access information and interact with teachers and other students.

Distance learning is also an important factor in stimulating student motivation. In order for students to be interested in learning, it is necessary to create interactive assignments, conduct online meetings and discussions, and provide opportunities to communicate with their colleagues.

Finally, the effectiveness of distance learning is determined by the individual characteristics of each student. Some students are better able to absorb information through visual materials, others through audio recordings, and others through practical tasks.

Distance learning has a number of advantages over traditional teaching methods. It allows students to gain knowledge and skills without having to visit an institution in person. This is especially important for those who live in remote areas or have limited mobility.

Distance learning also helps to reduce the time and cost of training. Students can study the materials at their own time and pace without having to travel to the institution. In addition, they can use various resources such as video tutorials, online courses, and tests to test their knowledge and improve their level.

Finally, distance learning provides students with more opportunities to work independently and develop their skills. They can choose the courses that best suit their interests and needs, as well as work on projects and assignments at their own pace. Another important feature of distance learning is the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning to create more effective learning programs. These technologies help

to adapt the educational material to the level of knowledge and interests of each student, as well as provide an opportunity for automatic assessment of knowledge and recommendations for improvement.

In addition, modern distance learning actively uses social networks and platforms for the exchange of experience and knowledge between students and teachers. This allows you to build communities of like-minded people and share experiences and knowledge in real-time.

Main part. Virtual laboratories are a powerful tool for learning and research, which allows students and scientists to gain new knowledge and skills in an interactive way.

Virtual labs are special online platforms that allow students and scientists to conduct experiments and research in a virtual environment. V. V. Trukhina reveals the content of the concept of "virtual laboratories" as a software and hardware complex focused on the formation of practical skills through a laboratory installation with remote access, based on software and hardware for plant control and data processing, including communication tools [Trukhin, 2002].

Working in a virtual laboratory can be very interesting and useful for students[7]. It allows them to gain experience with the latest technologies and research methods, as well as develop their data analysis and problem-solving skills. Work in a virtual laboratory may include conducting experiments, analyzing results, and creating progress reports [Dozorov, 2012]. Students can also participate in scientific research by working together with other students and scientists.

The organization of a virtual laboratory includes several stages:

Defining the goals and objectives of the laboratory:

Software selection: There are many software packages for organizing virtual laboratories, such as MATLAB, Python, LabVIEW, and others. The choice of software depends on the specific goals and objectives of the laboratory.

Create virtual models and experiments: In this step, you create virtual models of

objects, processes, and experiments that will be used in the lab.

User training: After creating a virtual lab, you need to train users on how to use the software and conduct experiments. Training can be conducted both in full-time and distance format. **Data collection and analysis:** After conducting experiments, the data obtained should be collected and analyzed to evaluate the effectiveness of the virtual laboratory and make adjustments if necessary.

Regular Lab Updates: To keep the Virtual Lab up to date, it is necessary to regularly update and supplement it with new models, experiments, and techniques.

It is important to note that working in a virtual laboratory requires discipline and responsibility. Students should monitor the deadlines for completing assignments and the quality of their work.

The organization of students to work in the virtual laboratory includes several stages:

1. Choosing the topic and goals of the study. At this stage, students choose a topic for their research and determine what tasks they want to solve.
2. Preparation of equipment and materials. Students must prepare all the necessary equipment and materials to conduct an experiment or research.
3. Creation of a virtual environment. Students create a virtual environment that will be used to simulate physical processes or other experiments.
4. Conducting an experiment or research. Students conduct an experiment or research in a virtual environment using a variety of methods and technologies.
5. Analysis of the results and creation of a report. After conducting an experiment or research, students analyze the results obtained and draw up a report on the work done.

Such virtual laboratories include the Logokot (<https://logokot.me/>) platform, developed by a group of specialists. This platform allows speech therapy students to form practical skills in examining and correcting speech disorders in children. Thus, in the process of conducting practical classes on the Logokot platform, speech therapist students mastered this server, which made it possible to perform many types of

corrective work that are provided for by the curriculum.

The structure of the web server of this platform includes the following service components:

1. A personal account that stores information about remedial work for each child
2. Knowledge base, which provides methodological recommendations in all areas of correctional work.
3. Speech therapy examination, which allows you to examine the child from pronunciation disorders of individual sounds to general speech underdevelopment of the ONR level I.
4. Didactic multimedia material for the correction of speech disorders.

Organizing educational distance practical classes can be challenging, but with the right approach, it can be successful.

The Logokot speech therapy platform allows you not only to examine children, but also offers a wide range of areas of correctional work.

Virtual examination of children by speech therapy students can be organized as follows:

The goals and objectives of the virtual survey are determined. It is determined what skills and knowledge students should receive as a result of work.

An introductory briefing is conducted. It is explained to students how the virtual survey will take place, what materials they will use, what tasks they will have to complete.

Preparation for the virtual examination: Students learn the methods and techniques of the virtual examination, get acquainted with the software necessary to conduct the virtual examination.

Taking medical history: Students collect all the necessary information about the child from the parents, such as age, gender, speech history, etc., and also receive permission to conduct a virtual examination. When simulating an examination, this point is omitted, but when conducting classes with a child online, it is mandatory.

Conducting a virtual examination: Students use the Logokot platform to examine the

child, and then carry out remedial work on the platform.

Thus, speech therapy students were given the task to examine children with speech therapy conclusions in virtual mode: General speech underdevelopment of the ONR level III. Pseudobulbar dysarthria; General speech underdevelopment of the ONR level III. Extrapiramidal dysarthria; Phonetic-phonemic underdevelopment of speech. Functional dyslalia; Phonetic-phonemic underdevelopment of speech. Erased dysarthria. Of course, these tasks were productive, but in order to simulate the examination, the student had to know the structure of this disorder according to the clinical-pedagogical and psychological-pedagogical classifications. And as a result of the examination, students should come to this speech therapy conclusion, i.e. they should know which parameters of the examination are present in the structure of the defect, and which should be excluded.

Tasks of a more complex level include the following:

According to the conclusion of the MPPK, at the time of admission to the speech therapy group, the child had a speech therapy conclusion: General speech underdevelopment of the ONR level I. Motor alalia. What, in your opinion, will be the speech therapy conclusion after two years of corrective work with the child (Subject to qualified assistance and the presence of positive dynamics).

Analysis of the results: after conducting a virtual examination, students analyze the data obtained and draw conclusions about the state of the child's speech development, analyze the speech map that was typed by the program based on the results of the examination. Analysis of the speech map makes it possible to assess the correctness of students' understanding of the structure of speech disorders [Akimenko, 2014, p.9].

Drawing up a conclusion: on the basis of the virtual examination, the program gives a version of the speech therapy conclusion, and students compare the speech therapy conclusion issued by the program with the state of the child's speech development.

Presentation of results: Students present the results of a virtual survey to a

teacher who evaluates their work and gives feedback.

Monitoring the performance of tasks by students. The teacher uses the platform's tools to monitor the completion of assignments by students.

Evaluation of students' work. At the end of the lesson, students' work is evaluated and feedback is given.

Regularity of such classes. Remote practical classes should be held regularly so that students can consolidate the skills they have learned.

These tasks required students not only to know the structure of the defect, but also to understand the dynamics of correctional work. Speech therapists, modeling the examination, came to the conclusion that working according to this program, the examination process becomes more qualitative and objective, and the speech map offered by the program speeds up and facilitates the examination process. The results of the examination are reflected in the speech chart, which is automatically filled in by the program and used by the speech therapist in correctional work.

Based on the results of the survey, the platform offers directions for an individual route of correctional work for the child. Speech therapists, having compared the initial data of the child's speech development and the speech map, came to the conclusion that the directions of correctional work are quite adequate.

Along with traditional methods of correctional work, the computer program offers modern developmental methods and techniques for correcting fine and articulatory motor skills, phonemic disorders, speech breathing, voice, vocabulary development, grammar and coherent speech [Akimenko, 2009, p.3].

As a result of the examination and correctional work, students noted that:

- exercises are effective and help to achieve your goals;
- exercises are diverse, colorfully decorated;
- exercises help to better absorb the material and develop the skills necessary for successful study.

One of the benefits of a virtual lab is that it allows students to conduct experiments from the comfort of their homes. This is especially useful for students who

live far from the institute or have limited opportunities to attend classes.

In addition, the virtual laboratory can help students better understand the principle of the examination and many areas of remedial work. This can be especially useful for young professionals starting out as speech therapists or for those who plan to work in science or technology.

In general, the high feedback of students about the virtual laboratory may be due to its convenience, accessibility and the ability to conduct examination and correctional work at a convenient time for students.

Conclusion

Thus, the use of virtual laboratories, to which we refer the LogoKot speech therapy platform, will allow you to master many types of correctional work in the mode of modeling working situations: conducting a speech therapy examination of the child, correcting speech development deficiencies, as well as consolidating and mastering various activities, from studying theory to drawing up a report on the study. However, virtual labs cannot completely replace traditional labs, as they do not give students the opportunity to work with real-world objects and materials, or to fully develop practical skills. Virtual labs are not a complete substitute for real-world lab experiences, and they cannot be used for all types of experiments and can significantly improve the educational process.

References

1. Akimenko V.M. Correction of sound pronunciation in children. Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2009. 142 p.
2. Akimenko V.M. Speech therapy examination of children with speech disorders. Rostov-on-Don: Feniks, 2014. 78p.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

3. Akimenko V.M. Developing lexical and grammatical classes. Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 127 p.
4. Distance Education // Problems of Informatization of Higher School, 1995. № 3. pp.44–45.
5. Dozorov V. A., Dozorov E. V. Virtual Laboratory Practicum as One of the Effective Forms of the Lesson in an Innovative School: Collection of Materials of the III International Scientific and Practical Conference "Organization of Pre-University Training in the Conditions of the Unified State Exam". Omsk, 2012. pp. 27–31.
6. Kechiev, L. N., Aleshin, A. V. Distance learning on the Internet, Vneshkolnik, 2001. № 11. pp. 19–21.
7. Tolstik A.M. Primenenie komp'yuternykh laboratornykh raboty – simulatorov v distantsionnom obuchenii [Application of computer laboratory work – simulators in distance learning]. Tomsk, 2000. № 1. pp. 49–52.
8. Trukhin A. V. Ispol'zovanie virtual'nykh laboratorov v obrazovanii [Use of virtual laboratories in education]. 2002. № 4. P.67–69
9. Sorokina, N. A. Kompleksnaya diagnostika razvitiya detey s rechevymi narusheniyami [Comprehensive diagnostics of the development of children with speech disorders]. Moscow: Vlados Publ., 2013. 116 p.